

Equal-Life First wave scientific papers

Project title: Early Environmental quality and life-course mental health effects
 Project Number: 874724
 Project Acronym: Equal-Life

Work package 10 - Deliverable D10.9

HISTORY OF CHANGES		
Version	Publication date	Change
1.1	2-12-2021	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Initial version, shared with PIs
1.2	22-12-2021	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Amended following comments by PIs
Def	24-12-2021	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Final version

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H2020 program	Grant agreement numbers 874724 (Equal-Life),
Project start date: Jan 1 st 2020	Duration: 60 months
Project Coördinators: Irene van Kamp (RIVM)	

WP (number and title)	WP10: Management and Dissemination
Deliverable Number	D10.9
Deliverable Title	First wave scientific papers
Due date	M24
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Dissemination Level	Public

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1 Summary

This report gives an overview of the published scientific papers published between January 1st 2020 and December 31st 2021 in the context of the Equal-Life project (*Chapter 2*) and a list of papers per workpackage (WP) that are in the final stages of preparation in December 2021, to be submitted early 2022 (*Chapter 3*). For the Equal-Life publication policy, we refer to D10.2.

2 Published papers

The following scientific papers were published between January 1st 2020 and December 31st 2021 in the context of the Equal-Life project:

- Miliias, V., & Psyllidis, A. (2021). Assessing the influence of point-of-interest features on the classification of place categories. *Computers, Environment and Urban Systems*, 86, [101597]. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compenvurbsys.2021.101597> (related to Task 5.3)
- Whipp, A. M., Vuoksima, E., Korhonen, T., Pool, R., But, A., Ligthart, L., Hagenbeek, F. A., Bartels, M., Bogl, L. H., Pulkkinen, L., Rose, R. J., Boomsma, D. I., & Kaprio, J. (2021). Ketone body 3-hydroxybutyrate as a biomarker of aggression. *Scientific Reports*, 11(1), 1-10. [5813]. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-84635-6> (related to Milestone 2.2)
- van Kamp, Irene, Kerstin Persson Waye, Katja Kanninen, John Gulliver, Alessandro Bozzon, Achilleas Psyllidis, Hendriek Boshuizen et al. "Early environmental quality and life-course mental health effects: The Equal-Life project." *Environmental Epidemiology* 6, no. 1 (2022): e183. doi: 10.1097/EE9.0000000000000183
- Conference paper by Maud Dohmen, Ella Braat-Eggen, Astrid Kemperman, Maarten Hornikx. A new approach for measuring space-time-activity-exposure patterns of children [full paper 33888.pdf \(icben.org\)](https://www.icben.org/full_paper_33888.pdf)

These papers (except for the conference paper) are also added to the continuous reporting module in the EC portal.

3 Papers in final stages of preparation

The following papers are in the final stages of preparation in December 2021 and will be submitted early 2022.

WP2:

- (Working) title: "Branched chain amino acids linked to depression in young adults"
Target journal: Journal for Affective Disorders

WP3:

- (Working) title: "Noise indicators relating to non-auditory health effects in children - A systematic literature review"
Target journal: International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health
Authors: Michail Evangelos Terzakis, Maud Dohmen, Irene van Kampen, Maarten Hornikx

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WP4:

- (Working) title: "The Social Exposome - A new conceptual framework"
Target journal: Environmental Health Perspectives
Authors: Gabriele Bolte, Lena Gudi-Mindermann, Maddie White, Jana Roczen
- Conference paper (planned 2022): pilot results children's exposure patterns (*related to the activity pattern in-depth study*)
Authors: Maud Dohmen and others.
- Journal paper (planned December 2022): Children's exposure patterns in relation to health and wellbeing
Target journal: to be decided
Authors: Maud Dohmen and others.

WP5:

- (Working) title: "Accessibility and spatial age segregation"
Target journal: Computational Urban Science (Special issue: Use of spaces, places, and points of interest)
Authors: Vasileios Miliadis, Achilleas Psyllidis, Alessandro Bozzon
- (Working) title: "Evaluating accessibility of urban greenspaces for active routine usage by children and adolescents"
Target journal: Landscape and Urban Planning.
Authors: Roos Teeuwen, Achilleas Psyllidis, Alessandro Bozzon, Gerd Kortuem
- (Working) title: "Stress fatigue and the built environment"
Target journal: Health & Place
Authors: George Aalbers, Vasileios Miliadis, Achilleas Psyllidis

Planned papers, not specifically related to one of the WPs:

- Journal paper (planned 2022): systematic review effects on noise on cognition and motivation in children 0-21 years old
Target journal: to be decided
Author(s): Maud Dohmen and others

